

Medina Baktybay

Assem Seitkali

Aikerim Manat

MT-2306

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Comparative Analysis of female Beauty and Fashion Video Advertising in the U.S. and South
Korea: Perceptions of a Kazakhstani Audience

Abstract

This research examined how beauty and fashion video advertisements from the United States and South Korea differ in their visual and cultural strategies, and how these differences are perceived by a Kazakhstani audience. Using a mixed-methods approach that combined content analysis and a quantitative survey, the study explored how global and local values intersect in beauty communication. Findings showed that U.S. ads emphasized individuality, empowerment, and authenticity, portraying beauty as self-expression, whereas South Korean ads focused on harmony, emotional connection, and collective ideals, framing beauty as a shared cultural value. Kazakhstani audiences viewed both styles as similarly authentic and engaging, suggesting the emergence of a shared global advertising language where cultural nuances remain influential.

Overall, the study highlights that global beauty advertising is not uniform but shaped by the dynamic interaction between global trends and local values. A strong link between perceived idealization and appearance comparison confirmed that idealized portrayals continue to affect self-perception regardless of origin. The results underscore the need for advertisers to balance authenticity with idealization and adapt campaigns to cultural attitudes toward individuality and community. Although the small survey sample and limited ad selection restrict generalizability, the research contributes to understanding how beauty ideals are constructed and interpreted across cultures, emphasizing the continued relevance of cultural context in globalized media.

Introduction

Background

Our group has an interest in media analysis because, as Media Technologies students, our specialty is focused on studying media platforms and their content. Since we frequently see ads and use social media every day, we often notice certain patterns in video advertising. One recent case was the GAP ad with Katseye, which was compared to the American Eagle jeans ad with Sydney Sweeney. The American Eagle ad was criticized for being too sexualized, especially when contrasted with the GAP commercial, and this sparked conflict on social media. We thought this example shows how U.S. ads often sexualize women, while, in contrast, Korean ads usually present women as innocent and pretty.

We chose the United States and South Korea specifically because both countries are major global players in media and advertising, yet they represent very different cultural approaches to portraying women. The U.S. advertising industry is one of the most influential worldwide, shaping global trends through Hollywood, social media platforms, and international brands. Its tendency to sexualize women has been widely critiqued and offers insight into how Western ideals of femininity are exported across borders. South Korea, on the other hand, has rapidly grown into a cultural powerhouse through K-pop, K-dramas, and global fashion and beauty industries. Korean media often presents women as innocent, pure, and youthful, creating another set of narrow ideals that are spreading internationally with the rise of the Korean Wave (Hallyu). Because the two cultures are very different, we wanted to compare how women are represented in these ads and how this may affect viewers. We believe this is important since such media can strongly shape self-esteem, self-perception, and identity, especially among teenage girls.

Problem

The issue we see is that video advertising often reinforces narrow and stereotypical images of women, which strongly influence how audiences - especially teenagers and young women - think

about themselves. In the United States, advertisements frequently rely on sexualization, portraying women as desirable objects rather than as multidimensional individuals. These portrayals normalize the idea that a woman's value is based on her physical attractiveness and sexuality. In South Korea, on the other hand, advertising more often frames women as innocent, delicate, and youthful, emphasizing purity and beauty above all else. While these approaches differ, both cultures end up limiting women to specific roles and ideals that do not reflect the full range of real-life identities and experiences. Constant exposure to such portrayals can have significant psychological effects, including lowered self-esteem, increased body dissatisfaction, pressure to conform to unrealistic beauty standards, and confusion about one's own identity. The problem is not just the stereotypes themselves, but also the lack of comparative understanding of how these different cultural contexts shape the influence of advertising. Without such knowledge, it is difficult to fully grasp how media affects self-perception globally, especially in a world where media content spreads across borders and young audiences are exposed to both local and international advertisements.

The goal of this research is to examine and compare the strategies, messages, and cultural contexts of video advertising in the United States and South Korea, and to analyze how these advertisements influence women's self-perception, identity construction, and social values within each cultural framework.

Our objectives include:

- To analyze how women are represented in U.S. and South Korean video advertisements, focusing on themes such as sexualization, innocence, empowerment, and diversity.

- To compare the cultural values reflected in advertising portrayals of women in both countries, using media and cultural frameworks.
- To examine how these portrayals may influence young women's self-perception, self-esteem, and body image in a globalized media environment.
- To investigate audience reactions to these portrayals by reviewing social media discourse (e.g., comments, online debates).
- To contribute to media literacy by raising awareness about how advertisements shape identity and self-worth, and by encouraging more critical engagement with media among audiences.

Research Questions

1. How do beauty and fashion video advertisements in the United States differ from those in South Korea?
2. How do these advertisements influence Kazakhstani viewers' self-perception and internalization of beauty standards?
3. Does the perceived authenticity or empowerment message of femvertising moderate its effect on self-esteem and body satisfaction among Kazakhstani viewers?
4. How do Kazakhstani audiences perceive representations of women in U.S. and South Korean beauty and fashion video advertisements?

This research can contribute to academic discussions about media influence, but it can also serve a practical purpose: encouraging media creators, educators, and consumers to think more critically about the messages they produce, share, and consume. For advertisers, such awareness can inspire more diverse and empowering representations of women that move beyond

stereotypes. For educators and parents, it can provide tools to help young people develop media literacy skills, enabling them to question harmful portrayals instead of internalizing them. For audiences, it can spark reflection about how the media shapes their self-image and identity. In this way, our study contributes to the bigger issue of how media can be used not only as a tool of persuasion and profit but also as a force for promoting healthier, more inclusive, and more realistic standards of identity and self-worth.

This paper first examines how video advertisements influence self-perception, particularly through representations of femininity, beauty, and empowerment. It then compares beauty and fashion advertising practices in the United States and South Korea, identifying differences in appeal types, celebrity usage, and cultural values. Finally, the study explores how Kazakhstani audiences perceive these contrasting advertising styles, analyzing whether exposure to idealized beauty imagery from either culture affects body satisfaction and self-concept.

Literature review

Influence of Video advertisements on self-perception

Advertising is the message that a company wishes to convey to its target audience (Habiba Moataz, 2023). The influence of video advertisements on self-perception has been a persistent subject of inquiry within media and consumer psychology. Existing scholarship indicates that advertising does not merely promote products but actively shapes individual self-concepts, particularly among women, by reinforcing or challenging societal standards of beauty, gender roles, and self-worth. (Habiba Moataz, 2023; Dai et al., 2025; Taylor & Costello, 2017)

Dai et al. (2025), Habiba Moataz (2023) and Koka (2025) suggest that traditional advertising frequently perpetuates idealized and stereotypical representations of femininity, emphasizing unattainable standards of thinness, youth, and physical perfection. Such portrayals have been consistently associated with body dissatisfaction, self-objectification, and lowered self-esteem (Dai et al., 2025; Taylor & Costello, 2017). Drawing on Social Comparison Theory (Festinger, 1954), these studies propose that viewers engage in upward comparisons when exposed to idealized models, resulting in unfavorable self-assessments and dissatisfaction with one's appearance. Similarly, Objectification Theory (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997) elucidates how repeated exposure to objectifying imagery encourages women to internalize an external observer's perspective, evaluating themselves primarily through appearance-based criteria.

Taylor and Costello (2017) found that the frequent depiction of extremely thin and youthful models in fashion advertising may foster harmful psychological effects, particularly among women who perceive a discrepancy between their own bodies and those of the models. Grau and Zotos (2016) further contend that such advertising practices reinforce systemic gender inequality by legitimizing narrow and distorted images of femininity as socially acceptable ideals. Koka (2025) characterizes this process as a form of secondary socialization, wherein advertising functions as a cultural agent that shapes perceptions of femininity, physical appearance, and appropriate social behavior. Over time, these mediated images contribute to internalized norms that may diminish women's sense of self-worth and reinforce conformity to socially constructed ideals.

While the psychological mechanisms underlying advertising's influence appear robust, their impact is culturally mediated. Vargas-Bianchi and Mensa (2020) note that cultural values, social norms, and media environments shape how audiences interpret representations of women in

advertising. In their study of young Peruvian consumers, they found that sexualized female imagery did not necessarily enhance brand recall, suggesting that objectification may fail to achieve marketing effectiveness in contexts where audiences are increasingly critical of gendered portrayals. This underscores the importance of context-sensitive advertising strategies that account for cultural diversity and audience awareness.

Recent developments in the advertising industry demonstrate a gradual shift toward inclusive and empowering portrayals of women. The rise of femvertising - advertising that challenges traditional gender stereotypes and promotes empowerment - represents an attempt to reverse the negative psychological effects of conventional advertising (Dai et al., 2025). Such campaigns are most effective when their messages are perceived as authentic and grounded in genuine representation rather than tokenistic diversity. Moataz (2023), in a qualitative study involving young women from diverse backgrounds, found that participants responded more positively to Aerie's "Share Your Spark!" campaign - featuring women of varying body types, skin tones, and ethnicities - than to Victoria's Secret's highly idealized portrayals. Participants reported that the inclusive imagery fostered feelings of representation, authenticity, and confidence, whereas exposure to traditional beauty standards evoked lower self-esteem and alienation. These findings indicate that representation and relatability play a critical role in mediating the psychological effects of advertising on self-perception.

Although advertising has often been implicated in reinforcing restrictive ideals, it also possesses the potential to serve as a positive socializing force. Koka (2025) argues that, when executed responsibly, advertising can inspire self-acceptance, promote active lifestyles, and encourage professional and personal growth. Similarly, Dai et al. (2025) highlight that femvertising's effectiveness depends on its perceived sincerity; campaigns that genuinely communicate

empowerment and inclusivity can contribute to healthier self-perception and more diverse standards of beauty. This duality underscores the evolving role of advertising as both an economic instrument and a sociocultural agent capable of influencing identity formation and self-concept.

Comparative Analysis of Beauty and Fashion Video Advertising in the U.S.

Beauty and fashion advertising in the United States represents a strategic form of visual communication that promotes products by appealing to consumers' desires for self-expression, confidence, and social approval. U.S. advertisements on digital platforms such as YouTube demonstrate a distinct preference for rational appeals, used in 38.6% of cases compared to only 19.8% in South Korea (Choi, 2021). This indicates that American consumers tend to favor advertising that provides clear and explicit reasoning rather than relying solely on emotional storytelling. Emotional appeals, however, remain highly prevalent, reflecting the dual nature of American advertising that balances rational persuasion with emotional connection (Choi, 2021). Unlike South Korea, where celebrities appear in over half of popular YouTube ads, the United States relies less on celebrity endorsement, but when celebrities are used, they tend to have a stronger product-related connection (Choi, 2021). This shows that American advertising focuses more on authenticity and informative communication than on symbolic association or idol-based influence. Therefore, such hypothesis has been developed:

H1: Rational and emotional appeals will be more balanced in U.S. advertisements, while celebrity endorsement will appear less frequently and be more product-related than symbolic.

While rationality and clarity characterize American advertising, it also carries emotional narratives rooted in the nation's cultural values of individualism, empowerment, and authenticity.

Considering this, the following hypothesis has been proposed:

H2: U.S. beauty and fashion video advertisements will predominantly emphasize individualism, empowerment, and authenticity, reflecting Western cultural values of self-expression and independence.

Despite the progressive tone of modern campaigns, cosmetic advertising continues to reproduce traditional gendered messages (McCabe et al., 2017). Women recognize how influential advertising has been in shaping their perceptions of beauty and internalize and resist the cosmetic discourse simultaneously, embracing ideals of outer beauty while seeking to reconcile them with inner authenticity (McCabe et al., 2017). The imagery in cosmetic advertising still privileges external appearance and reinforces gender hierarchies, suggesting that gender bias remains deeply rooted in both society and marketing practices (McCabe et al., 2017).

A global comparison further illustrates how beauty ideals in the United States differ from those in other regions. U.S. advertisements frequently feature tanned models, fuller lips, and sensual expressions, traits associated with vitality, fertility, and sexual confidence (Spyropoulou et al., 2020). In contrast, East Asian countries such as South Korea, Japan, and China favor lighter skin and youthful, delicate features that emphasize innocence and purity (Spyropoulou et al., 2020). These distinctions show that American beauty standards are closely tied to ideals of independence, empowerment, and sex appeal, making beauty a symbol not only of physical attractiveness but also of social success and confidence (Spyropoulou et al., 2020).

Beneath this surface of empowerment lies a persistent issue of sexual objectification.

Mainstream American media, including advertisements, television, and magazines, often portray women as sexual objects through revealing clothing, body-centered camera angles, and an emphasis on physical appeal over personality or competence (Ward et al., 2023). Such portrayals perpetuate patriarchal norms and strengthen the association between women's value and their appearance (Ward et al., 2023). Exposure to these objectifying messages has been linked to the internalization of sexist beliefs and the reinforcement of traditional gender roles, which ultimately limit women's representation and self-perception (Ward et al., 2023).

Comparative Analysis of Beauty and Fashion Video Advertising in South Korea.

South Korea's beauty and fashion advertising industry has become one of the most influential in Asia, shaped by a strong cultural emphasis on appearance, innovations in media, and the global spread of K-pop and K-beauty. Numerous scholars have examined the importance of the beauty, the influence of beauty standards and the spread of K-pop within South Korean society. Building on these findings, a researcher suggests that the perception of bodily and facial beauty is deeply intertwined with social value and interaction in South Korea (Gelézeau, 2015). In the context of South Korean society, beauty standards are highly strict and socially reinforced, contemporary Korean women and men display an intense preoccupation with bodily aesthetics and appearance, marked by confidence and an emphasis on physical refinement (Gelézeau, 2015).

The beauty standards in East Asian countries such as Korea, China, and Japan, models are often characterized by smaller facial features and pointed chins, reflecting local beauty ideals.

Traditionally, fair skin has been associated with wealth and social status, as it implied a lifestyle protected from outdoor labor. (Spyropoulou et al., 2020). The scholar additionally suggests that this perception continues to hold in these more conservative societies. Conversely, in Western

nations such as the U.S., Australia, and affluent parts of Europe, tanned skin is often viewed as a sign of affluence and leisure, suggesting one can afford vacations and outdoor recreation. In East and Southeast Asian contexts, including Korea, a small mouth and youthful, almost childlike appearance are considered attractive traits. In contrast, Western and other global beauty markets such as the U.S., Latin America, and other countries tend to favor fuller lips and more mature facial aesthetics (Spyropoulou et al., 2020). These findings highlight the striking contrasts between the United States and South Korea; however, the study also reveals that one universal beauty standard remains consistent across both contexts: straight, white teeth and a balanced smile line that either slightly reveals the gums or covers the upper portion of the teeth are universally regarded as desirable features (Spyropoulou et al., 2020). Given these distinctions, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H3: South Korean beauty and fashion advertisements will portray women with lighter skin, smaller facial features, and youthful appearances, while U.S. advertisements will emphasize tanned skin tones, fuller lips, and more mature aesthetics.

In the South Korean context, the pursuit of such beauty ideals is closely tied to the rise of K-pop culture, where physical appearance is considered an integral component of celebrity identity and marketability. K-pop's extensive media reach has been shown to influence not only global entertainment preferences but also broader lifestyle trends, including fashion and diet.

Consequently, advertising and PR practitioners are encouraged to capitalize on this synergy by embedding Korean products naturally within K-pop media, emphasizing their quality and aesthetic appeal to international audiences (Zhang et al., 2020). The "South Korean tidal wave"

(Hallyu) referring to the diffusion of popular cultural products such as television programs and K-pop across Asia since the early 2000s - has played a significant role in disseminating beauty standards that position South Korea as a transnational benchmark for aesthetics (Gelézeau, 2015).

Within South Korean advertising, this principle aligns closely with the global spread of K-pop and its integration into marketing practices. K-pop functions not only as a cultural export but also as a vehicle for brand communication, visually contextualizing South Korea's image as a producer of innovative, high-quality goods. Through music videos, celebrity endorsements, and product placements, K-pop media reinforces brand familiarity and strengthens consumer attitudes toward Korean products (Zhang et al., 2020). Consequently, the study hypothesizes that:

H4: K-pop elements are widely utilized in South Korean beauty and fashion advertisements as a strategic tool to enhance brand appeal and cultural influence.

However, another research suggests that messages and media content related to beauty and diet products, especially those endorsed by popular celebrities, may exert a stronger persuasive influence on audiences in the United States than on those in South Korea (Jung et al., 2016).

Advertising appeals used in popular online video ads on YouTube in South Korea were largely similar to those in the United States, suggesting a convergence of advertising strategies across culturally distinct contexts. The only notable variations were the higher frequency of rational appeals and celebrity endorsements in South Korean ads (Choi, 2021). Video advertising in South Korea differs from commercials in Russia, Europe, and the United States. Koreans rarely use UGC content (user-generated content), meaning content created by users themselves -

commercial videos are completely different. Most of them are mesmerizing, beautifully shot, and flawless in every aspect, featuring various special effects, the latest technological innovations, and media trends, all designed not to overshadow but to emphasize and harmonize with the beauty of the idol on screen (Tereshchenko, 2025). Both countries' most-viewed YouTube ads predominantly employed individualistic rather than collectivistic appeals, indicating that Western advertising values increasingly shape Korean advertising practices. Emotional appeals were more common than rational ones in both contexts, implying that emotion-driven advertising resonates universally, regardless of cultural background (Choi, 2021). The greater reliance on celebrity endorsers in South Korea highlights a culturally specific strategy reflecting the country's strong celebrity culture and idol industry. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H5: South Korean advertisements will display a greater reliance on celebrity endorsements and idealized portrayals of beauty, aligning with collectivist and appearance-oriented cultural norms.

Comparison of Kazakhstani people's perceptions of U.S. and South Korean cultures.

Perceptions of foreign cultures in Kazakhstan are shaped by both admiration and criticism, depending on how cultural values align or clash with local norms. Several studies reveal a contrast between how Kazakhstani youth view South Korean culture, particularly through the lens of the Korean Wave (Hallyu), and how U.S. culture is perceived in relation to values, lifestyle, and media. (Uatay et al., 2018; Suh et al., 2021). This leads to the following hypothesis:

H6: Kazakhstani audiences will evaluate South Korean advertisements more positively than U.S. advertisements due to cultural familiarity, media exposure to K-pop, and shared values.

A strong pattern emerges in the literature: South Korean culture is viewed favorably by many young people in Kazakhstan. Bakytzhanova and Tuleshova (2023) document that the increasing availability of internet access has enabled widespread exposure to K-pop, dramas, fashion, and cosmetics among Kazakhstanis. This exposure has contributed to perceiving Korea as “cool,” modern, and attractive. Youth tend to prefer Korean products, especially in cosmetics and apparel, and follow Korean styles, adopting aspects of culture beyond entertainment into lifestyle choices (Bakytzhanova & Tuleshova, 2023).

Uatay et al. (2018) similarly find that likability, image, and visit intention related to Korean entertainment (dramas, pop music) are positively correlated. Young people in Kazakhstan report admiration for Korean stars and emulate Korean fashion and beauty trends. This admiration translates into seeking Korean cultural information, adopting aesthetic styles, and considering travel or cultural engagement. The Korean Wave thus functions not only as entertainment but also as a soft-power mechanism that influences self-expression and identity among Kazakhstani youth (Uatay et al., 2018). Hence, the following hypothesis is suggested:

H7: Exposure to idealized beauty portrayals from either cultural context will be associated with higher levels of self-objectification and body dissatisfaction among Kazakhstani viewers.

Suh et al. (2020) contribute additional nuance: the more globalized Kazakh consumers believe the Korean Wave is, the more positive their attitudes toward Korean products and Korea itself. These perceptions also influence purchase intentions for Korean goods. In Islamic cultural

contexts, such as many parts of Kazakhstan, the perception of authenticity and respect for local norms or compatibility enhances the country-of-origin effect (Suh et al., 2020).

In contrast, perceptions of U.S. culture among Kazakhstani audiences tend to be more ambivalent or critical. Laruelle and Royce (2021) conducted focus groups that revealed widespread disapproval of certain U.S. cultural values, especially where these are viewed as conflicting with Kazakhstani familial, sexual, or moral norms. Among 93 participants, only a very small minority assessed U.S. influence positively; many described U.S. cultural values as “amoral,” “deviant,” or undermining traditional sexual or family values (Laruelle & Royce, 2021). Topics such as homosexuality, divorce, feminism, or hyper-individualism were especially frequent as points of concern.

Although some participants acknowledge positive aspects of U.S. culture, such as encouragement of self-confidence, entrepreneurship, and innovation, these traits are often interpreted ambivalently. They are sometimes seen as double-edged: while offering opportunities, they are also viewed as promoting individualism at the cost of community, or materialism over social cohesion (Laruelle & Royce, 2021). Despite somewhat negative Kazakhstani people’s views of U.S. culture, the study tests the following hypothesis, to show the positive aspects of U.S. influence:

H8: Advertisements perceived as authentic, empowering, and inclusive will foster more positive self-perception and body satisfaction among Kazakhstani audiences, regardless of their country of origin.

Similarly, while U.S. culture has influence, via media, business, technology, the negative perceptions are strongest where values conflict with local religious, familial, or moral

frameworks (Laruelle & Royce, 2021). Thus, U.S. culture is sometimes embraced for its economic or educational ideals, but cultural practices, lifestyle depictions, or media content that clash with conservative norms are critically viewed.

Research gap

Although numerous studies have examined representations of women in advertising across Western and East Asian contexts, there remains a striking absence of research exploring how audiences in Central Asia, particularly Kazakhstan, perceive and interpret these portrayals. Existing scholarship primarily focuses on Western consumers or the domestic audiences of South Korea, offering limited insight into how cross-cultural beauty ideals are received in other sociocultural environments. Moreover, little to no research addresses the beauty and fashion industries in relation to Kazakhstani consumers, despite the growing influence of both American and Korean media in shaping local beauty standards. Current literature also overlooks how cultural proximity, media exposure, and value systems shape Kazakhstani viewers' responses to these contrasting aesthetic narratives. Therefore, this study seeks to fill this gap by conducting a comparative analysis of U.S. and South Korean female beauty and fashion video advertisements and examining their perception among Kazakhstani audiences.

Research Questions and Hypotheses

Building on the identified research gap, the present study examines how Kazakhstani audiences perceive female beauty and fashion video advertisements from the United States and South Korea. While prior studies have extensively analyzed Western and East Asian advertising, little is known about how audiences from post-Soviet, culturally hybrid societies interpret these contrasting beauty ideals. This research therefore aims to explore how exposure to differing

cultural representations of femininity shapes self-perception, body image, and attitudes toward advertising among Kazakhstani viewers.

Research Questions

5. How do beauty and fashion video advertisements in the United States differ from those in South Korea?
6. How do these advertisements influence Kazakhstani viewers' self-perception and internalization of beauty standards?
7. Does the perceived authenticity or empowerment message of femvertising moderate its effect on self-esteem and body satisfaction among Kazakhstani viewers?
8. How do Kazakhstani audiences perceive representations of women in U.S. and South Korean beauty and fashion video advertisements?

Methodology

This study employs a mixed-methods research design, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a comprehensive understanding of how beauty and fashion video advertisements from the United States and South Korea are perceived by a Kazakhstani audience. The mixed-methods approach was chosen because it allows for both statistical analysis of audience perceptions and in-depth exploration of cultural and visual elements in advertisements.

To address Research Questions 1 and 4 and test Hypotheses H1–H5, a qualitative content analysis was conducted on selected U.S. and South Korean advertisements, focusing on recurring visual and narrative patterns such as authenticity, emotional appeal, and representation of women (Choi, 2021; Spyropoulou et al., 2020).

To address Research Questions 2 and 3 and test Hypotheses H6–H8, a quantitative survey was conducted among Kazakhstani viewers to measure perceptions, emotional responses, and attitudes toward these ads, focusing on variables such as likability, body satisfaction, and perceived authenticity (Uatay et al., 2018; Suh et al., 2020)

Kazakhstan provides a unique context as a culturally hybrid society influenced by both Western and East Asian media. Kazakhstani youth are increasingly drawn to K-pop and K-beauty (Uatay et al., 2018), while U.S. culture is viewed ambivalently, admired for innovation but often criticized for its values (Laruelle & Royce, 2021). This duality makes Kazakhstan an ideal setting to explore how global beauty ideals are interpreted within a post-Soviet, multicultural society.

Together, these methods offer both textual and empirical insights into the cultural and psychological effects of beauty advertising, providing a well-rounded cross-cultural perspective.

Similar approaches have proven effective in examining cultural and perceptual dynamics in previous research. For instance, Laruelle and Royce (2021) employed surveys and focus groups across Kazakhstan to capture nuanced public perceptions, demonstrating the effectiveness of combining quantitative and qualitative methods in exploring attitudes shaped by cultural and geopolitical contexts. Likewise, Bakytzhanova and Tuleshova (2023) utilized both a structural approach and survey research to assess the diffusion of the Korean Wave in Kazakhstan, confirming the suitability of mixed methodologies for studying transnational cultural influence. Thus, surveys seem to be the most effective way to statistically identify patterns in opinions of a large group of people. Furthermore, Choi (2021) analyzed U.S. and South Korean YouTube advertisements through a systematic coding scheme, integrating quantitative and qualitative

measures to classify cultural and emotional appeals. Consequently, content analysis is the most suitable method to study cultural differences and/or similarities.

The chosen participants for the study are Kazakhstani women of the age from 16 to 30 who are the potential users of beauty and fashion products and they were selected by judgmental sampling method to ensure accurate results. Data sources for the content analysis are makeup, skincare and clothes' brands advertisements from Youtube, TikTok and Instagram since these are the most commonly used social media apps by both brands and consumers of them.

The survey was conducted online via the Google Forms platform and distributed among the respondents. In a similar approach, Jung et al. (2016) examined the associations between attitudes toward cosmetic surgery, celebrity worship, and body image among South Korean and U.S. female college students. In their study, a total of 370 female undergraduates were recruited for a survey from a South Korean university and a university in the mid-Atlantic region of the U.S., following Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval from both institutions. All participants were volunteers, recruited from undergraduate courses across the university campuses.

Survey questions:

General Perception of Advertising

1. How familiar are you with South Korean popular culture (e.g., K-pop, K-dramas, fashion)?
2. How often do you come across advertisements from South Korea?
3. How often do you come across advertisements from the United States?

4. Which country's advertisements feel closer to your values, style, and emotions?
5. To what extent do you agree with the statement:
“Advertisements from South Korea align more with my cultural values than those from the U.S.”
6. How important is appearance in your social environment?

Evaluation of U.S. Advertisement

https://youtu.be/iZonhmCmqEs?si=f_zBA0O7LAs16zAY - U.S Beauty ad

Rate the advertisement on a scale from 1 to 5:

- Unclear – Clear
- Insincere – Authentic
- Boring – Emotionally engaging
- Unrealistic – Realistic
- Uncomfortable – Comfortable

Evaluation of South Korean Advertisement

<https://vm.tiktok.com/ZMAVQj4JL/> - South Korean beauty ad

Rate the advertisement on a scale from 1 to 5:

- Unclear – Clear
- Insincere – Authentic
- Boring – Emotionally engaging
- Unrealistic – Realistic
- Uncomfortable – Comfortable

Comparison and Reflections

1. How would you describe the appearance of the models in the advertisements you just saw?
2. How often do you compare your appearance to people shown in advertisements?
3. After viewing the advertisements, how did you feel about your own appearance?
4. To what extent do you agree with the statement:
“These ads made me think more critically about my body or appearance.”
5. Which advertisement presented more realistic or attainable beauty standards?
6. Which advertisement made you feel more pressured to look a certain way?

For the content analysis, advertisements were categorized into three groups: makeup, skincare, and clothing. These categories were chosen because they represent the most commonly used types of products among the female audience in both the U.S. and South Korea. Additionally, previous studies (Choi, 2021; Spyropoulou et al., 2020) have highlighted a lack of diversity in the types of products analyzed, justifying this selection. A qualitative content analysis was conducted on a total of 30 advertisements—five makeup, five skincare, and five clothing ads from each country (the U.S. and South Korea). The advertisements were randomly selected within each product category to ensure an equal number of ads for both countries, but there was the main criterias for all of them which is to be commercial advertisement and to be from the past 5 years. For reference, the study by Choi (2021) analyzed 101 unduplicated online video ads from each country (202 in total), distributed across various categories: entertaining (30 ads), digital device/service (21 ads), food/beverage (15 ads), personal care/health (11 ads), automobile (6 ads), fashion (4 ads), and miscellaneous (14 ads).

For the analysis of this data, we have chosen to apply a coding method in order to identify recurring patterns that can either support or challenge our hypotheses. This approach allows for a systematic examination of visual and thematic elements across the selected advertisements, helping to uncover relationships between variables such as celebrity presence, cultural values, and beauty ideals. By assigning specific codes to observable features, the data becomes more structured and comparable across countries. This method is supported by the work of Spyropoulou et al. (2020), in their study, coding was used to explore the model characteristics and cultural contexts.

Findings

To systematically analyze the advertisements, a structured coding framework was developed, consisting of five main categories: General Information, Appeal Type, Celebrity Endorsement, Cultural Values, and Beauty Representation. Each category includes variables that allow the identification of consistent patterns across both U.S. and South Korean advertisements.

The General Information category includes descriptive variables that provide essential contextual details for each advertisement. These include the country of origin, brand name, year of release, platform. These factors help classify the data and allow the comparison of advertisements based on where and how they were produced or distributed.

The Appeal Type category is designed to test H1, which assumes that U.S. advertisements tend to use more emotional appeals, while South Korean advertisements rely more on rational appeals. To assess this, variables such as primary appeal type, rational appeal indicators, emotional appeal indicators, and visual focus were included. These variables distinguish between

advertisements that emphasize product information, benefits, and ingredients (rational appeals) and those that rely on emotional storytelling, mood, or aspirational imagery (emotional appeals).

The Celebrity Endorsement category relates to H1, H4, and H5 and examines how the presence and type of celebrities influence advertising messages. The variables measure the presence of celebrity, celebrity type. These variables are particularly relevant in cross-cultural comparison because celebrity usage reflects both marketing strategies and cultural norms.

The Cultural Values category operationalizes H2 and H5, focusing on the representation of individualistic versus collectivist cultural traits. The variables individualism, empowerment, authenticity, and collectivism/social belonging were selected to capture how advertisements reflect broader societal ideals. Western advertisements are expected to highlight self-expression, empowerment, and personal authenticity, whereas South Korean ads may emphasize group harmony, social approval, and shared beauty ideals.

The Beauty Representation category addresses H3 and H5, which focus on how physical appearance and beauty ideals differ between the two countries. The variables include dominant skin tone, facial features emphasized, age portrayal, body type, makeup style, and idealization level.

To test H6, a chi-square goodness of fit test was conducted to examine whether the observed distribution of advertisement preference differed from the expected pattern. Based on prior cultural exposure trends and the assumption that Kazakhstani audiences are increasingly familiar with South Korean media, it was expected that participants would show a stronger preference for South Korean advertisements (40% or 12 participants), moderate preference for U.S. advertisements and for both ads equally (27% each, or 8 participants each), and a low rate of

rejection (6% or 2 participants). The observed frequencies (South Korea = 8, U.S. = 10, Both = 10, None = 2) did not significantly deviate from the expected distribution, $\chi^2(3, N = 30) = 2.33, p = .51$. Formula used:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$

In addition to preference, mean evaluation scores for each advertisement were compared to determine whether familiarity with Korean culture translated into higher perceived quality. The South Korean advertisement (M = 3.02) and the U.S. advertisement (M = 3.04) received nearly identical average ratings across the five evaluated attributes (clarity, authenticity, engagement, realism, comfort). These results indicate that, although participants were moderately familiar with South Korean culture, this did not lead to a statistically significant preference or more favorable evaluation of Korean advertising content.

To test H7, a Spearman rank-order correlation was used to explore the relationship between the perceived idealization of advertising models and the frequency of appearance comparison among participants. The variable “idealization” was derived from the question “*How would you describe the appearance of the models in the advertisements you just watched?*” (1 = realistic, 2 = somewhat idealized, 3 = highly idealized). The variable “appearance comparison” was based on responses to “*How often do you compare your appearance to people depicted in advertisements?*” rated on a 1–5 scale. The correlation analysis revealed a strong positive association, $\rho(30) = .86, p < .01$, indicating that participants who perceived the ads as more idealized tended to compare their appearance more frequently to the featured models. Formula used:

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum D^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

This finding supports H7, confirming that exposure to idealized portrayals in beauty advertisements is linked to increased self-objectification and body-related self-awareness. As shown in Figure 1, higher perceived idealization levels correspond to greater tendencies toward appearance comparison, demonstrating how advertising imagery can reinforce social beauty standards.

Figure 1. Spearman rank-order correlation graph.

To test H8, average ratings for *authenticity*, *realism*, and *comfort* were calculated for both advertisements to determine whether the perceived emotional tone of an ad affects self-perception regardless of its origin. The mean composite score for the U.S. advertisement was 2.97, while the South Korean advertisement received a similar average of 3.00, suggesting minimal difference in perceived authenticity and inclusivity between the two. Also, most participants did not show any changes of their self-perception after watching the ads (N = 25), meaning that no matter the origin of the ad, the participant's self-confidence does not change.

Discussion

This section discusses the results of the content analysis and survey, interpreting the cultural and aesthetic distinctions between U.S. and South Korean beauty advertisements. The analysis across skincare, makeup, and clothing categories revealed notable contrasts in appeal types, celebrity presence, and cultural values, while the survey of Kazakhstani viewers highlighted similar perceptions of authenticity and emotional engagement across both countries, though idealized imagery tended to enhance self-comparison.

- Appeal Type

Emotional appeals dominated in all categories and in both countries, yet the balance between emotional and rational elements varied. U.S. advertisements, particularly for makeup, demonstrated a more balanced approach combining emotional tone with rational product information, highlighting features and benefits. South Korean advertisements, in contrast, relied almost exclusively on emotional appeals, emphasizing mood, visuals, and symbolic storytelling rather than product features. This differs from what has been found by Choi (2021), stating that emotional appeals appeared with similar frequency in both.

In skincare and clothing categories, both markets primarily used emotional framing, but Korean ads incorporated it as a central persuasive tool, enhancing aesthetic appeal and symbolic storytelling. U.S. ads tended to combine emotional resonance with messages of authenticity and clarity. In makeup advertising, U.S. brands displayed a more rational structure, whereas none of the Korean makeup ads contained rational content, aligning with Choi's (2021) findings, which showed that rational appeals were significantly more frequent in U.S. advertisements than in South Korean ones. This suggests that U.S. advertising aims to balance emotional engagement

with product credibility, while Korean advertising focuses on affective experience and idealized imagery.

- **Celebrity Endorsement**

The findings showed that celebrity endorsement played an equally important role in both U.S. and South Korean advertising, indicating that the use of public figures has become a universal strategy rather than a culturally distinct one. Although the overall frequency of celebrity presence was similar, the *types* of celebrities differed, reflecting each country's cultural and industrial priorities. South Korean ads relied heavily on K-pop idols and models, highlighting the close relationship between commercial branding and the entertainment industry. This supports Tereshchenko's (2025) observation that Korean advertising emphasizes visual harmony and idol aesthetics to enhance emotional engagement. In contrast, U.S. advertisements featured a broader mix of singers, actors, models, and influencers, suggesting a focus on authenticity, diversity, and relatability. The consistent celebrity presence across skincare, makeup, and clothing categories in both contexts suggests that fame-driven promotion has become a shared global marketing language.

However, these results differ from Choi (2021), who found that South Korean ads featured celebrities more frequently than U.S. ones. The similarity observed in this study may reflect recent shifts in global advertising, where American brands increasingly rely on celebrity and influencer culture to attract online audiences. This convergence suggests that national advertising styles are becoming less distinct as both markets respond to similar global media trends and consumer expectations.

- **Cultural Values**

Regarding skincare, signs of both individualism and collectivism were present and represented more in U.S. ads, while empowerment and authenticity indicators in Korean ads seemed to be seen more. However, despite such differences, it can be said that both countries' skincare advertisements value individuality and authenticity. These results are similar to the previous findings by Choi (2021), who observed that U.S. and Korean ads did not differ from each other in terms of individualistic and collectivistic appeals. These outcomes may stem from cultural shifts and the growing influence of online media, where emotionally engaging and personalized content tends to attract more attention.

Nevertheless, unlike Choi's (2021) study, if talking about makeup and clothing brands' advertisements, this research identifies that the distinction became more evident between these two countries. To be exact, U.S. ads clearly emphasized individualism and empowerment, often portraying confidence, self-expression, and authenticity as central values. In contrast, South Korean ads leaned toward collectivism and social belonging, where beauty was depicted as a shared ideal rather than an individual pursuit. Which may be caused due to the differing cultural values and societal expectations in each country, where Western cultures typically prioritize self-expression and independence, while South Korean culture places greater emphasis on harmony, conformity, and maintaining social cohesion. Gelézeau (2015) highlighted the predominant role of physical appearance in South Korean society, noting that the appearance of both the body and face plays a crucial role in social life.

In this study, South Korean advertisements consistently presented themes of harmony and group identity, aligning beauty with social connection and shared standards. Meanwhile, American advertisements framed beauty as a reflection of inner confidence and personal choice. The strong presence of authenticity in both markets, however, aligns with McCabe et al. (2017) view that

makeup rituals unite inner and outer beauty as part of embodied experience, suggesting that authenticity operates as a universal aesthetic value across cultures. This might be due to Westernization and digital media influence, which have significantly shaped local beauty perceptions. Gelézeau (2015) noted that in South Korea, the promotion of Western standards of beauty has become an integral part of defining Korean beauty itself, particularly in contrast to Japanese aesthetic ideals, from which a deliberate distance is maintained. In this sense, the findings align with the idea that the global influence of digital media, transnational beauty trends, and the ongoing process of Westernization collectively promote self-expression and authenticity

- **Beauty Representation**

Beauty representation findings reveal striking aesthetic contrasts. As predicted, South Korean ads consistently featured models with very light skin tones, small and delicate facial features, and youthful appearances (teens to early 20s). This can be explained by the previous studies by Spyropoulou et al. (2020), which claims that the women that look young and cute, nearly childlike, are considered attractive in China, Japan, Thailand, and Korea. Furthermore, high levels of idealization, particularly in skincare and makeup ads, reinforce Korea's appearance-oriented culture and the societal value placed on maintaining an idealized image. Jung et al. (2016) noted that Korean women's beauty standards emphasize not only facial attractiveness but also obtainment of idealized figures, which supports our hypothesis.

U.S. advertisements, by contrast, portrayed a wider diversity of skin tones (from light to tan and dark) and more mature, realistic portrayals of beauty. Fuller lips, pronounced features, and inclusivity of different racial representations reflect an ongoing cultural shift toward diversity and authenticity. As noted by Spyropoulou et al. (2020), U.S. models have fuller lips.

Idealization levels were moderate, with several realistic portrayals, especially in clothing advertisements, supporting that U.S. beauty ideals emphasize maturity and individuality. The contrast in makeup styles further underlines these cultural distinctions: Korean ads favored dewy/glowy looks symbolizing youth and vitality, whereas U.S. ads displayed a mix of matte, glamorous, and natural styles, aligning with varied expressions of personality and lifestyle.

Survey discussion

Cultural familiarity with South Korean media and exposure to K-pop did not translate into a stronger liking or higher evaluation of Korean advertisements, which differs from Laruelle and Royce's (2021) study stating that Kazakhstani audience perceives U.S. negatively, and Bakytzhanova and Tuleshova's (2023) findings which identifies Korean culture as very positive for Kazakhstani people. Even though Korean culture is highly visible in Kazakhstan, the similar ratings for both ads suggest that people no longer view Korean advertising as something distinct or novel. Instead, they seem to perceive both U.S. and Korean ads as part of the same modern, visually appealing, and professional media environment. This shows that advertising influence may depend less on cultural exposure and more on universal features such as design quality, storytelling, and emotional tone.

The strong positive relationship between how idealized participants found the models and how often they compared themselves to them highlights an important psychological pattern. Viewers who described the ads as highly idealized were also more likely to compare their appearance to the people in them, aligning with Moataz's (2023) study where he found that women often compare their physical appearance, lifestyles, financial situations with what they see on digital media. This means that regardless of whether the ad came from the U.S. or South Korea, seeing

flawless and polished beauty standards triggered self-evaluative thoughts. It demonstrates how easily advertising can influence self-image, even among viewers who are aware that such portrayals are unrealistic.

The minimal difference in perceived authenticity, realism, and comfort between the two ads shows that emotional tone and inclusivity did not have a major effect on self-confidence. Most participants reported feeling the same about themselves after watching both advertisements. This suggests that while people recognize when an ad feels authentic or well-made, it does not necessarily change how they feel about their own appearance or value.

Conclusion

This research explored how beauty and fashion video advertisements from the United States and South Korea differ in their visual and cultural strategies and how these differences are perceived by a Kazakhstani audience. Using a mixed-methods design that combined content analysis and a quantitative survey, the study provided a comprehensive perspective on how global and local values intersect in beauty communication.

The findings revealed that despite the globalization of media aesthetics, cultural identity continues to shape advertising strategies. U.S. advertisements emphasized individuality, empowerment, and authenticity, representing beauty as a form of self-expression and confidence. In contrast, South Korean advertisements focused on harmony, emotional connection, and collective ideals, portraying beauty as a shared cultural value. Both markets demonstrated a strong reliance on celebrity endorsement, yet the types of celebrities differed - U.S. brands featured diverse public figures, while South Korean brands primarily used idols, reinforcing idealized and emotionally appealing imagery.

The survey among Kazakhstani viewers showed that audiences perceived both U.S. and South Korean ads as similarly authentic and emotionally engaging. This suggests that the increasing exposure to international media has created a shared global advertising language, where cultural distinctions are subtle but still influential. However, a strong relationship between perceived idealization and appearance comparison confirmed that idealized portrayals in advertisements continue to shape viewers' self-perception, regardless of the ad's cultural origin.

Overall, this study contributes to cross-cultural advertising research by demonstrating how localized cultural patterns persist within globalized beauty communication. It highlights that effective advertising must consider not only aesthetic appeal but also cultural expectations and emotional resonance. For practitioners, the findings suggest the importance of balancing authenticity and idealization, and of tailoring campaigns to align with cultural attitudes toward individuality and community.

By analyzing both visual content and audience responses, the study enhances understanding of how beauty ideals are constructed, circulated, and interpreted across different societies.

Ultimately, it shows that global beauty advertising is not culturally uniform but rather a dynamic exchange where global and local meanings continuously interact.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the survey sample was relatively small ($n = 30$), which restricts the generalizability of the findings. Moreover, since the questionnaire consisted mainly of closed-ended items (from "yes" to "no" or on Likert-type scales), participants may have provided superficial or random responses rather than reflective evaluations. Regarding the content analysis, only 30 advertisements were examined, and their selection was random rather than based on popularity or engagement metrics. This may have

limited representativeness, as the sample might not fully capture dominant advertising trends or the most influential campaigns in each country. These findings suggest that advertisers should adapt their messages to cultural expectations—focusing on authenticity and self-expression for Western audiences and emotional, visually balanced storytelling for East Asian markets.

This paper first discusses several examples of existing research on how video advertisements influence self-perception, particularly through representations of femininity, beauty, and empowerment. It then compares beauty and fashion advertising practices in the United States and South Korea, identifying differences in appeal types, celebrity usage, and cultural values. Finally, the study explores how Kazakhstani audiences perceive these contrasting advertising styles, analyzing whether exposure to idealized beauty imagery from either culture affects body satisfaction and self-concept.

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Appendix A

Общее восприятие рекламы

Насколько вы знакомы с южнокорейской популярной культурой (например, К-поп, дорамы, мода)? [Копировать диаграмму](#)

30 ответов

Как часто вы видите рекламу из Южной Кореи?

30 ответов

Как часто вы видите рекламу из США?

30 ответов

Рекламу какой страны вы считаете ближе себе по ценностям, стилю и эмоциям?

30 ответов

Насколько вы согласны с утверждением: «Реклама из Южной Кореи ближе к моим культурным ценностям, чем реклама из США.»

30 ответов

Насколько важна внешность в вашем окружении?

30 ответов

Оценка рекламы из США

Оцените рекламу по данным характеристикам от 1 до 5

[Копировать диаграмму](#)

Оценка рекламы из Южной Кореи

Оцените рекламу по данным характеристикам от 1 до 5

[Копировать диаграмму](#)

Сравнение и размышления

Как бы вы описали внешность моделей из рекламы, которую вы только что посмотрели? [Копировать диаграмму](#)

30 ответов

Как часто вы сравниваете свою внешность с людьми, изображёнными в рекламе?

30 ответов

После просмотра реклам выше, как вы почувствовали себя по поводу своей внешности?

30 ответов

В какой степени вы согласны со следующим утверждением: «Эта реклама заставила меня задуматься более критически о своём теле или внешности.»

30 ответов

Какая реклама показала более реалистичные или достижимые стандарты красоты?

30 ответов

Какая реклама заставила вас чувствовать большее давление, связанное с необходимостью выглядеть определённым образом?

30 ответов

Appendix B

Consent form

Comparative Analysis of Beauty and Fashion Video Advertising in the U.S. and South

Korea: Perceptions of a Kazakhstani Audience

Researchers: Manat Aikerim, Seitkali Assem, Baktybay Medina

Institution: Astana IT University

You are invited to participate in the survey, conducted by Manat Aikerim, Seitkali Assem, Baktybay Medina from Astana IT University. The purpose of the study is to examine and compare the strategies, messages, and cultural contexts of video advertising in the United States and South Korea, and to analyze how these advertisements influence the perception of Kazakhstani audiences.

Participation in this project is entirely voluntary. Participants are free to withdraw from the study at any time and/or request the withdrawal of their data, without any penalty or negative consequences.

For this project, participants will be asked only to complete a survey in Google Forms. No audio or video recordings will be taken, and the only information retained will be the survey responses provided.

All responses will be treated with strict confidentiality. No identifying information will be collected, and all data will be anonymized. The results will be reported in aggregate form only, ensuring that no individual participant can be identified.

The collected data will be stored securely as statistical charts accessible only to the researchers. The data will be retained for the duration of the project and will be permanently destroyed six months after the completion of the study.

Upon completion of the survey, participants will be provided with a short debriefing statement explaining the purpose of the research in more detail. If participants are interested, a summary of the overall research findings will be shared with them once the project is finalized.

Appendix C

Links to video advertisings

Skincare

Kim JiWon X MEDIHEAL Skincare Ads -

<https://youtu.be/ShF02-Cw6P4?si=cspTI9WbEckbzs4->

COSRX provides vibrant, glowing skin to everyone -

https://youtu.be/_7VZBIu28yo?si=LvQBatp2u9JAKdRc

이니스프리 X 윈영이와 함께하는 수분체력 키우기 틱톡으로 GO! -

<https://youtu.be/i4XvzVAwSTk?si=7M7uUUvGn6ks8opb>

Discover the Power Of Pine! - <https://vm.tiktok.com/ZMAgudYQ9/>

바쿠치올 세럼 사용 꿀팁 -

<https://www.instagram.com/reel/DE12-WYyglV/?igsh=MTZ0eWV6YWR0NHN6dQ==>

Hailey Bieber - We Don't Bite | World Of Rhode | Rhode Skin -

<https://youtu.be/2Sd1UMnT-sk?si=6TO32CpfJzbIzZln>

Dior Skin Essentials - https://youtu.be/RxFkGHPyJj8?si=XejX0a-q_5rOvZMq

Laneige Water Bank Starring Sydney Sweeney -

<https://youtu.be/0t4OZCkFUso?si=ifLbvFRrGhlXKRi9>

#CeraVePartner This song has been stuck in my head for 2 weeks straight @CeraVe #heyitsme -

<https://vm.tiktok.com/ZMAVCgVoN/>

BEAUTY STOP-AND-GO. A quick refresh and beauty boost - all in a minute. -

<https://vm.tiktok.com/ZMAVCWjHM/>

Makeup

GiGi Hadid | New Super Stay Matte Ink Lipstick Birthday Edition - Maybelline -

<https://youtu.be/t7z7bF-M-WA?si=1ievA7nmFa9HzpIL>

Panorama Mascara - See Life In Panorama | L'Oréal Paris® Australia & New Zealand -

<https://youtu.be/vk-M4nSVOhU?si=pMAIjkM0iZDZtNf9>

When I started @Rare Beauty, I set out to create a brand that celebrates you—

every side of you. - <https://vm.tiktok.com/ZMAVCrGnJ/>

We love foundation - <https://vm.tiktok.com/ZMAVCyMUv/>

A little BLUSH FOR a little FLUSH. -

<https://www.instagram.com/reel/C8CiQ9zJh4R/?igsh=ZGt0OWQybWt1NWQ0>

Clio's heart has been struck by an arrow From Apple YUJIN! -

<https://vm.tiktok.com/ZMAggPH3Y/>

MAC Cosmetics Korean Ad By LISA MANOBAN -

<https://youtu.be/9jm2pLZ0e0E?si=nRMsgRTNikFUEBoL>

POWDER LIP & CHEEK with AMUSE girl WON YOUNG -

<https://vm.tiktok.com/ZMAVC4cTB/>

Our ambassador Chaewon, the talented singer and leader of South Korean group Le Sserafim, reveals her individuality by creating four different looks with of our new Artist Face Powders. -

<https://vm.tiktok.com/ZMAVCTQT1/>

Happy JISOO Day! -

<https://www.instagram.com/reel/Cm8uKT3K3RH/?igsh=bHcxazMzdzdob3B0>

Clothing

8seconds X MINJUKIM with LIZ -

https://www.instagram.com/reel/DOrys2Nk_dl/?igsh=eTRsa2YyZXp1cGNh

#CoachMatinKim, designed to inspire the loner and lover in all of us (with a little help from #KATSEYE). -

<https://www.instagram.com/reel/DEDrjnESnQ-/?igsh=MWFnNDVodHRvdWFsZQ==>

Minji, Hanni, Danielle, Haerin and Hyein in Calvin Klein | Spring 2025 Campaign -

<https://youtu.be/14KqQhzPvBg?si=kggFGbeTJVCdLAhX>

[New Balance] Time to Winter 빛나는 겨울을 맞이할 시간. 뉴발란스 액티브 다운(Full) -

<https://youtu.be/T9HPZc15SLI?si=UB0ctq4mVXeqXWKG>

#LSAFashionObsessions: Seeing red - <https://vm.tiktok.com/ZMAV4kkPX/>

Chapter 2: “Pool Hall” reimagined with Beyoncé | LEVI’S® -

<https://youtu.be/y2o2FuqMtxI?si=1KIkGHZs1yKBpHxV>

As seen on our brand ambassador Suki Waterhouse, Fall’s new Hamilton Moderne is the bag you’ll want to take everywhere. -

<https://www.instagram.com/reel/DNntavTAUo-/?igsh=MWVyZGtYXdiMXhidA==>

This season, #RalphLauren creates cinematic tensions between the landscapes of the West and #RLCollection's Modern Romantics: a wardrobe of Italian artistry and a fearlessly personal style.

- <https://www.instagram.com/reel/DPjeWsOkUWf/?igsh=MTlyMW0xd2d6NDV1Ng==>

Better in Denim. - <https://vm.tiktok.com/ZMAgaqDfR/>

Sydney Sweeney Has Great Jeans | American Eagle -

<https://youtu.be/AK8s3iqL99c?si=qZIG10TMEQUoBnK7>

Tables from content analysis.

Skincare

1. General Information. Table 1

Variable	Codes									
	USA					KOREA				
Brand name	Rhode Skin	Dior Skin	Laneige	Cerave	Chanel	Mediheal	Cosrx	Innisfree	RoundLab	Bywishtrend
Year of release	2022	2025	2022	2025	2025	2021	2024	2022	2024	2025
Platform (1 =YouTube / 2 = Instagram & TikTok)	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	2

2. Appeal Type (H1). Table 2

Variable	Codes									
	USA					KOREA				
Commercial	Rhode Skin	Dior Skin	Laneige	Cerave	Chanel	Mediheal	Cosrx	Innisfree	RoundLab	Bywishtrend
Primary appeal type (1 = Rational / 2 = Emotional / 3 = Balanced)	2	2	1	3	2	3	3	2	2	1

(0 = No / 1 = Yes										
Celebrity type (1 = K-pop idol / 2 = Actor/Actress / 3 = Model / 4 = Influencer / 5 = Other)	4	1;2;3	2	4	2	1	1	1	3	3

4. Cultural Values (H2 & H5). Table 4

Variable	Codes									
	USA					KOREA				
Commercial	Rhode Skin	Dior Skin	Laneige	Cerave	Chanel	Mediheal	Cosrx	Innisfree	RoundLab	Bywhishtrend
Individualism (0 = Absent / 1 = Moderate / 2 = Strong)	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Empowerment (0 = Absent / 1 = Moderate / 2 = Strong)	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	1

Authenticity (0 = Absent / 1 = Moderate / 2 = Strong)	1	0	2	2	0	2	0	2	2	2
Collectivism / Social belonging (0 = Absent / 1 = Moderate / 2 = Strong)	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

5. Beauty Representation (H3 & H5). Table 5

Variable	Codes									
	USA					KOREA				
Commercial	Rhode Skin	Dior Skin	Laneige	Cerave	Chanel	Mediheal	Cosrx	Innisfree	RoundLab	Bywhishtrend
Dominant skin tone (1 = Very light / 2 = Light / 3 = Medium / 4 = Tan/Dark)	3	All races	2	All Races	2	1	1	1	1	1
Facial features emphasized	2	Mixed	2	Mixed	2	1	1	1	1	1

(1 = Small/Delicate / 2 = Fuller lips / pronounced features / 3 = Neutral)										
Age portrayal (1 = Youthful (teen/early 20s) / 2 = Mature (late 20s+))	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1
Idealization level (0 = Realistic / 1 = Moderately idealized / 2 = Highly idealized)	1	1	0	0	1	2	1	2	2	1

Makeup

1. General Information. Table 6

Variable		
	USA	KOREA

Brand name	Maybelline	L'Oréal	Rare Beauty	We Love Foundation	Rhode	MAC Korea	Amuse	Make Up For Ever	Dior	Clio
Year of release	2022	2024	2024	2025	2024	2020	2025	2023	2023	2025
Platform (1 =YouTube / 2 = Instagram & TikTok)	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2

2. Appeal Type (H1). Table 7

Variable	Codes									
	USA					KOREA				
Commercial	Maybelline	L'Oréal	Rare Beauty	We Love Foundation	Rhode	MAC Korea	Amuse	Make Up For Ever	Dior	Clio
Primary appeal type (1 = Rational / 2 = Emotional / 3 = Balanced)	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	2	3	2
Rational appeal indicators (0 = Absent / 1 = Present)	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0

Emotional appeal indicators (0 = Absent / 1 = Present)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Visual focus (1 = Product-centered / 2 = People-centered / 3 = Balanced)	3	1	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	2

3. Celebrity Endorsement (H1 & H4 & H5). Table 8

Variable	Codes									
	USA					KOREA				
Commercial	Maybelline	L'Oréal	Rare Beauty	We Love Foundation	Rhode	MAC Korea	Amuse	Make Up For Ever	Dior	Clio
Presence of celebrity(ies) (0 = No / 1 = Yes)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Celebrity type (1 = K-pop idol / 2 = Singer)	3	3	5 (Singer)	5 (Singer)	4	1	1	1	1	1

= Actor/Actress / 3 = Model / 4 = Influencer / 5 = Other)										
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4. Cultural Values (H2 & H5). Table 9

Variable	Codes									
	USA					KOREA				
Commercial	Maybelline	L'Oréal	Rare Beauty	We Love Foundation	Rhode	MAC Korea	Amuse	Make Up For Ever	Dior	Clio
Individualism (0 = Absent / 1 = Moderate / 2 = Strong)	1	2	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0
Empowerment (0 = Absent / 1 = Moderate / 2 = Strong)	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1
Authenticity (0 = Absent / 1 = Moderate / 2 = Strong)	1	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1

Collectivism / Social belonging (0 = Absent / 1 = Moderate / 2 = Strong)	0	0	1	0	0	2	2	2	2	2
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5. Beauty Representation (H3 & H5). Table 10

Variable	Codes									
	USA					KOREA				
Commercial	Maybelline	L'Oréal	Rare Beauty	We Love Foundation	Rhode	MAC Korea	Amuse	Make Up For Ever	Dior	Clio
Dominant skin tone (1 = Very light / 2 = Light / 3 = Medium / 4 = Tan/Dark)	2	2	3	2	3	1	1	1	1	1
Facial features emphasized (1 = Small/Delicate / 2 = Fuller lips / pronounced)	3	2	2	3	3	1	1	1	1	1

features / 3 = Neutral)										
Age portrayal (1 = Youthful (teen/early 20s) / 2 = Mature (late 20s+))	2	1	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1
Makeup style (1 = Natural / 2 = Dewy/Glowy / 3 = Glamorous / 4 = Matte)	4	3	1	3	2	2	2	2	2	2
Idealization level (0 = Realistic / 1 = Moderately idealized / 2 = Highly idealized)	1	2	0	1	1	2	1	1	2	2

Clothing.

1. General Information. Table 11

Variable	Codes									
	USA					KOREA				
Brand name	Levi's	American Eagle	GAP	Michael Kors	Ralph Lauren	New Balance	Calvin Klein	MINJUKIM	Matin Kim	Puma
Year of release	2025	2025	2025	2025	2025	2024	2025	2025	2024	2024
Platform (1 =YouTube / 2 = Instagram & TikTok)	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2

2. Appeal Type (H1). Table 12

Variable	Codes									
	USA					KOREA				
Commercial	Levi's	American Eagle	GAP	Michael Kors	Ralph Lauren	New Balance	Calvin Klein	MINJUKIM	Matin Kim	Puma
Primary appeal type (1 = Rational / 2 = Emotional / 3 = Balanced)	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	2
Rational appeal indicators (0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

= Absent / 1 = Present)										
Emotional appeal indicators (0 = Absent / 1 = Present)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Visual focus (1 = Product-centered / 2 = People-centered / 3 = Balanced)	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3

3. Celebrity Endorsement (H1 & H4 & H5). Table 13

Variable	Codes									
	USA					KOREA				
Commercial	Levi's	American Eagle	GAP	Michael Kors	Ralph Lauren	New Balance	Calvin Klein	MINJUKIM	Matin Kim	Puma
Presence of celebrity(ies) (0 = No / 1 = Yes)	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1

Celebrity type (1 = K-pop idol / 2 = Actor/Actress / 3 = Model / 4 = Influencer / 5 = Other)	5 (Singer)	2	5 (Group)	5 (Singer)	3	1	1	1	5 (Group)	1
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4. Cultural Values (H2 & H5). Table 14

Variable	Codes									
	USA					KOREA				
Commercial	Levi's	American Eagle	GAP	Michael Kors	Ralph Lauren	New Balance	Calvin Klein	MINJUKI M	Matin Kim	Puma
Individualism (0 = Absent / 1 = Moderate / 2 = Strong)	1	2	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0
Empowerment (0 = Absent / 1 = Moderate / 2 = Strong)	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1
Authenticity (0 = Absent /	1	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1

1 = Moderate / 2 = Strong)										
Collectivism / Social belonging (0 = Absent / 1 = Moderate / 2 = Strong)	0	0	1	0	0	2	2	2	2	2

5. Beauty Representation (H3 & H5). Table 15

Variable	Codes									
	USA					KOREA				
Commercial	Levi's	American Eagle	GAP	Michael Kors	Ralph Lauren	New Balance	Calvin Klein	MINJUKI M	Matin Kim	Puma
Dominant skin tone (1 = Very light / 2 = Light / 3 = Medium / 4 = Tan/Dark)	4	2	2;3;4	2	2;3;4	1	1	1	2;3;4	1
Age portrayal (1 = Youthful (teen/early 20s) / 2 =	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	1	1	2

Mature (late 20s+))										
Body type (1 = Slim / 2 = Curvy / 3 = Athletic / 4 = Other)	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Idealization level (0 = Realistic / 1 = Moderately idealized / 2 = Highly idealized)	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0